

CHEMICAL ASPECTS OF INTERFACE ADHESION BETWEEN
ELECTROLYTICALLY OXIDISED CARBON FIBRES AND EPOXY RESINS.

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ABSTRACT

The chemical contribution to the adhesion of electrolytically oxidised carbon fibres in resin is investigated using a novel adaptation of a derivitization technique. Adsorption isotherms are plotted from X.P.S. spectra by monitoring the uptake of magnesium on the fibres as a function of concentration of treatment solution. The isotherms show chemisorption to COOH groups on the treated fibres and physisorption to other oxygen groups on the untreated fibres. Auger parameters of the magnesium also indicate a move from isolated atoms to compounds on going from untreated fibres to high treatment levels. Values of acidity are calculated from the uptake of magnesium by COOH atoms. These show good correlation with mechanical data on the same system.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion; Carbon fibre; Adsorption; Interface; Surface Treatment.

1.INTRODUCTION

Surface treatments are applied to carbon fibres in order to optimize their adhesion to epoxy resin matrices. The mechanism and means by which this is achieved is not well understood. The measurement of this adhesion and mechanical contributions to the bond are the subject of another paper (1). Alternative contributions may be physical or chemical and these are discussed presently.

A range of oxygen containing species have been found on the surface of oxidised fibres, for example -COOH, -C=O and -C-OH. The amount of oxygen is known to increase with surface

treatment and in this work elemental analyses are carried out for each fibre type to investigate this further. However, there is a complex chemistry on the surface of the fibres and two different approaches have developed to discover the amount and distribution of the various functional groups. The first has been developed by Kozlowski et al (2) and is based on peak fitting the spectra for the proportions of groups present. This method is best suited to highly treated fibres but is less useful for levels of treatment often used in practice. The second, developed by Denison et al (3), involves labelling particular functional groups on the fibre by a reagent which is detectable by X.P.S. This derivitization method treats the fibre rather violently by boiling in saturated solutions and the present approach seeks to improve the technique by the use of less vigorous procedures.

The method is based on the idea of Castle and Ghosh (4) and considers the concept of monitoring the uptake as a function of the concentration of solution in which the fibre is labelled. This permits the determination of an adsorption isotherm. The fact that X.P.S. enables a direct measurement of atomic % uptake means that the isotherms can be analysed by classical theories for adsorption from solution or gaseous media. It is possible from the resultant isotherms to indicate the possibility of chemisorption compared with physisorption and the amount of acidic groups available for bonding on the fibre surface may be calculated.

In order to further investigate the difference between bonding potential of an untreated fibre and a treated fibre, the Auger Parameter of the reagent, in this case magnesium, was measured. This parameter, was first introduced by Wagner in 1975 (5) and is a convenient method of determination of chemical state. It may be used to ascertain whether the magnesium is bonding differently to the untreated fibre compared to the treated fibre which would reflect on the fibre's bonding potential to resin.

2.EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Surface Treatment Previously untreated and unsized high strength XA carbon fibres have been subjected to varying levels of an electrochemical treatment (1). The treatment consists of anodic oxidation in an electrolyte with varying degrees of current applied. Treatment levels are referred to by their charge density i.e. XA25 = XA fibre treated 25 coulombs/m²(c/m²).

2.2 Surface Analysis The elemental composition of the untreated and treated fibres were determined using X ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (X.P.S.). The fibre tows were cut into 3cm lengths, mounted on holders and transferred to the vacuum chamber for analysis. All spectra were recorded on a V.G. Scientific ESCALAB 11 at an operating pressure of 10⁻⁹ torr using Al K α radiation. The spectrometer was interfaced to a V.G.5000 data system.

The percentages of carbon, nitrogen and oxygen present for each treatment level are shown in fig.1, the scale for carbon on the right hand side. The histogram indicates that the level of oxygen and nitrogen rise with higher treatment whilst carbon drops accordingly. Average values for the fibres are shown in Table 1.

2.3 Adsorption Isotherms To investigate the functional groups in more detail, adsorption isotherms were constructed for selected fibre treatment levels. The uptake of magnesium ions by the carbon fibre was determined as a function of the concentration of $MgSO_4$ in a series of test solutions. In this case magnesium atoms are taken up by the COOH or COH groups on the surface of the carbon fibre in accord with the usual derivitisation mechanism (3).

Fibre tows were cut into 3cm lengths and placed in beakers containing solutions of different strengths of $MgSO_4$ at room temperature. The strengths of the solutions were all fractions of the saturation solubility (S_0). Fibres were soaked for 30min and then rinsed thoroughly in deionised water and dried in an oven at $60^\circ C$ for an hour. The procedure of obtaining spectra was the same as in the previous section.

Adsorption isotherms were plotted for XAU, XA10, XA25, XA100 and XA400. The uptake was determined from the atomic % of the element on the surface adjusted by the appropriate sensitivity factor and then corrected for excess magnesium associated with sulphate. An example of a typical isotherm is shown in fig.2 for XA25. The scatter is due to differences on the fibre surface between one part of the tow or another along its length and also from the centre to the outside of the tow. Scatter for XA10 was worse than for the other fibres.

The experimental isotherms were found to fit Langmuir isotherms reasonably well as shown in fig.2 for XA25 fibre. Langmuir's theory was the earliest of its kind and dealt with the equilibrium set up between an adsorbed gas and the adsorbent, the rate at which molecules condense on the sites of the adsorbent surface being equivalent to the rate at which they reevaporate. It assumes all sites are equivalent which may be valid in this situation if it is reasoned that the functional groups are very dispersed and should have little effect on each other.

The Langmuir isotherm (6), when applied to adsorption from solution becomes:

$$S/At\% = 1/Bxm + S/xm$$

xm = monolayer coverage or in this case every acidic group is occupied with one Mg atom

S = relative solubility $\hat{=}$ S/S_0 where S_0 maximum = 1

At% = Uptake of the atom

$B = A(\text{const})e^{q/RT}$ q = heat of adsorption

Values of x_m have been calculated for the fibres tested and these are shown in Table 1 to increase to level XA25 with no more significant increase after that. The XA100 data is shown in fig. 3 and can be seen to divide into two data sets forming two isotherms. This phenomena has been observed before by Ghosh (4). The amount of oxygen found on the surface is consistently higher (above 11.5 %) for the fibres on the upper isotherm.

Values of B are also shown in the table and these are related to the heat of adsorption . They can be seen to increase with surface treatment although in fact there may be two distinct groups - the low values of B , indicating physisorption, being characteristic of low levels of treatment.

From the values of x_m , the amount of acidity on the surface in the form of COOH groups may be calculated. The method of Denison has been applied which assumes an escape depth of 3.5nm for carbon and a surface segment of 40000 carbon atoms. From the density of graphite and diameter of the fibre a geometrical surface area is calculated so that the number of segments per gramme of fibre can be ascertained. The number of acidic groups per surface segment may be found from the percentage of magnesium compared to carbon present on the surface, (the amount of magnesium is half the amount of COOH to which it is bonded as it is divalent). So the acidity of the fibre can be calculated. These values may be seen in Table 1 and indicate a rise with treatment level. If these are plotted against treatment as shown in fig.4 it can be seen that the acidity begins to level off at XA25. The second XA100 value has been omitted from the present analysis and will be dealt with in a later section.

2.4 Auger Parameters The chemical state of the magnesium can investigated by observing the Auger Parameters. Wagner first introduced the concept of an Auger Parameter as the difference between the kinetic energy of an Auger line and a photoelectron line. Garenstroom and Winograd in 1977 (7) modified the parameter by effectively adding the photon energy $h\nu$ to the value of the Auger parameter α :

α = Binding energy Photoelectron - kinetic energy Auger electron

Wagner also introduced the Wagner plot (8) as a useful means of representing the modified Auger Parameter. The kinetic energy of the sharpest Auger line is plotted against the binding energy of the most intense photoelectron line. A shift from one leading diagonal to another represents a change in the Auger Parameter and a shift perpendicular to this indicates

differential charging of the sample. The Wagner plot for magnesium is illustrated in fig.5 and examples of values generated by Mg on fibres XAU,XA10,XA25 and XA100 are shown. There is evidence of a shift from one Auger parameter to another on going from XAU to XA10 and to XA25 . There is no difference between XA25 and XA100.

3.DISCUSSION

The level of oxygen and nitrogen on the surface of the fibre increases with treatment and continues to increase steadily with all treatments tested. The mechanical tests on the same data (1) showed that there was an important level at XA25 where the adhesion increased to a plateau value. Therefore the mechanical data cannot be directly related to the C/O ratios.

The adsorption isotherms indicate that COOH groups are found on the surface and that these increase up to XA25 and then begin to level off. This is in very good agreement with the mechanical data and seems to suggest that the adhesion strength may be related partly to the amount of acidity on the surface.

The second and much higher isotherm of XA100 needs further explanation. It has been verified that the higher isotherm is made up from samples with considerably higher oxygen content and therefore the anomaly is a function of fibre variability and not testing procedure. The shape of the isotherm is not the same as the other treated fibres which have a steep rise followed by a plateau indicative of chemisorption. The second XA100 fibre isotherm is more gently rising as with the untreated fibre. This indicates a more physical nature of adsorption.

It is appropriate at this point to discuss the values of the constant B. These are related to the heats of adsorption and values are much lower for the untreated fibre and the higher XA100 isotherm compared with the other treatment levels. This is consistent with the expectation of lower heats of adsorption for the more weakly bound physisorbed atoms. B is higher for XA10 and higher still for XA25, XA100 and XA400 demonstrating the probability of chemisorption. In the light of this information then, it must be pointed out that the values of acidity may not be directly compared when they are perhaps associated with a different type of acidity or bond. Therefore in a true comparison of COOH groups on the fibres the values of XAU and high XA100 must be withdrawn.

The reason for the high oxygen levels on the XA100 fibre may be related to the ideas proposed in the paper on mechanical aspects (1). Consider firstly the XA10 fibre which possesses more scatter compared with the other fibre levels. The oxygen levels match this scatter. It is thought

that the varying oxygen levels may be due to a weakly bound layer being removed at about this point. If the layer is fully removed there will be a different level of oxygen compared to a fibre which has some of the layer still attached. Once removed any residual stress may be released and cause more edge sites of the less ordered inner planes to unfold onto the surface. The COOH content would increase due to their greater tendency to form at edge sites. The treatment continues to increase the COOH level and smooth the fanned out edges of the planes up to XA25. From this point on no significant increase in adhesion is observed as probably all available sites are used up. However, at XA100 the surface becomes considerably rougher as shown by Robinson (9) and it is possible that cavitation is starting to occur. These cavities may be full of oxygen sites which promote bonding but not necessarily to COOH groups.

The Wagner plot is also consistent with the theory that the untreated fibre is bonding physically. The values for XAU are at much lower values compared to the treated fibres. The arrow indicates the position of isolated atoms e.g. gas . The more isolated the atom in behaviour, the less likely it is to be part of a compound.

4.CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that the electrolytic oxidative treatment improves adhesion by a complex mechanism which appears to involve the formation of COOH bonding sites. The acidity associated with these sites levels off by XA25 correlating well with mechanical data on the same system (1). The mechanism of adhesion therefore appears to alter from physical to chemical bonding on treatment of the fibre. It is suggested that this is not the only contribution to adhesion. There may be the removal of an outer layer of graphite leaving a stable surface with more edge sites available for bonding to the resin.

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Table 1.

Surface Treatment	0	10	25	100	400
Atomic % Carbon	92.3	86.2	85.7	81	81
Atomic % Nitrogen	3.93	5.1	6.51	7.9	8.16
Atomic % Oxygen	3.29	8.3	7.55	9.7	9.9
Monolayer xm %Mg	.8	.9	.98	1 (3)	1
Acidity $\mu\text{eq/g}$ *	6.03	7	7.6	8.4	8.75
Constant B	6.3	13	35	28(9)	47

* μ equivalent/gram

Fig.1. Elemental composition of the surface of untreated and treated carbon fibres.

Fig.2. Adsorption isotherm for magnesium uptake on XA25 fibre

Fig.3. Adsorption isotherm for magnesium uptake on XA100 fibre.

Fig.4. Acidity values for the surface of untreated and treated XA carbon fibres.

Fig.5. Wagner plot for magnesium on untreated and treated carbon fibres.